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FORMATION OF THE THYMUS OF THE OFFSPRING IN THE EARLY POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF TOXIC HEPATITIS OF THE MOTHER

Khasanov B.,

Bukhara State Medical Institute,

Department of Histology, Cytology and Embryology, Bukhara.

Duschanova R.

Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy,

Department of Physiology and Pathological Physiology,

Urgench, Uzbekistan

Abstract

On sexually mature female white outbred rats before pregnancy, chronic heliothrine intoxication was created, leading to the development of chronic aggressive hepatitis. The influence of chronic toxic hepatitis (CTG), on the development of the thymus of rat pups during the period of early postnatal ontogenesis was researched. It was found that against the background of mother's CTG, there is a decrease in the weight of rat pups 1-7 days and a lag in growth by 7-21 days after birth and development of rat pups after birth, a decrease in both the absolute and relative mass of the thymus up to 21 days after birth. Morphologically, there is a violation of the formation of the thymus, manifested in the lag in the development of the structural and functional zones of the thymus, due to an increase in the area occupied by the connective tissue stroma, accompanied by the phenomena of hypoplasia.

Keywords: early postnatal ontogenesis, chronic hepatitis, thymus development, rat pups.

In recent years, the understanding of the structure and function of this central organ of the immune system has expanded significantly. The morphological features and functional significance of various cells of the thymic microenvironment, the mechanisms of their interaction with differentiating thymocytes have been established [7]. Due to the development of a number of biologically active substances such as thymopoietin, thymosin, thymulin, etc., the thymus has a regulating effect on the immunological processes in the body [5, 6]. There have appeared works reflecting thymus condition and T-lymphocytes in various immunodeficiency conditions. At the same time, many aspects of the physiology and pathology of the thymus are still far from a final decision.

It is known that the thymus plays an extremely significant role in maintaining the body's immune homeostasis. In the thymus, proliferation and differentiation of T-lymphocytes occur, the leading role in these processes belongs to the cells of the thymic microenvironment.

One of the significant physiological conditions is the lactation period, however the issues of the peculiarities of changes in the thymus gland in the offspring during the period of mother's milk feeding are not suf-

ficiently illuminated and do not give a reliable representation of a deeper understanding of organ changes during breastfeeding, when various substances penetrate into the body of a growing child through the mother's milk having an adverse effect on the body of the newborn, in the case of pathology of the maternal body during this period [14].

It has been established that the development and formation of the immune system in the pre- and postnatal periods of development depends on a number of factors, including the condition of health of the maternal organism, which may affect the morphogenesis of the fetal immune defense organs. A number of authors are of the opinion that changes in the functional condition of the mother's body during pregnancy, caused by infectious diseases, taking medications, can negatively affect the development of the immune system of the offspring [16]. Particularly, recently, among women of childbearing age, there has been an increase in extra genital diseases, including the hepatobiliary system. Particular interest are researches of the effect of chronic hepatitis in the mother during pregnancy, on the development of the immune system of the offspring at different periods of postnatal development, including the thymus - the central organ of immunity [18, 21].

The thymus as the primary organ of the immune system largely determines not only the condition of the peripheral organs of immunogenesis, but also the severity of the protective reactions of the whole organism. Immunodeficiency condition in young children are quite common in clinical practice. Among the reasons leading to immunodeficiency, the predominant are unfavorable exogenous influences of various etiologies in the prenatal period of ontogenesis, as well as the presence of pathology of the maternal organism, not only in the prenatal period, but also during breastfeeding [17, 19]. At the same time, in the literature available to us, this issue remains poorly understood.

The aim of our research was to study the mother's chronic heliotrinic hepatitis on the development of the thymus of the offspring in the period of early postnatal ontogenesis.

Material and methods

The experiments were carried out on 50 sexually mature female white outbred rats weighing 130-150 g. All animals were quarantined for two weeks to exclude infectious diseases. Animals were divided into 2 groups (50 rats in each): experimental and control. A model of heliotrinic hepatitis was prepared by weekly administration of 0.05 mg of heliotrin per gram of body weight for 6 weeks [1]. The control group of animals received sterile saline instead of heliotrin. 10 days after the last injection, males were added to the females. In the future, the course of pregnancy was monitored. It should be noted that the experiments were carried out in accordance with the requirements of the "European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals Used for Experimental and Scientific Purposes" and the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki on the humane treatment of animals. The pups were decapitated under light ether anesthesia on the 1st, 3rd, 7th, 15th, 21st and 30th days after birth. Pieces of thymus, fixed in 12% neutral formalin or Bouin's liquid, were embedded in paraffin after appropriate wiring. Sections 5-7 μm thick were stained with hematoxylin and eosin and used for morphological and morphometric researches. Morphometric researches were carried out using the Avtandilov

grid per unit area according to the generally accepted method. Statistical processing of the data obtained was carried out using computer programs.

Results

Consequently to our morphological researches, it was found that in newborn rat pups (intact and control group) the thymus is sufficiently formed and consisted of two lobes. Outside, the thymus was covered with a capsule, from which connective tissue septa departed, dividing the lobes into lobules. The lobules are characterized by a clear differentiation into cortical and medullary substance, a high density of distribution of cells in the cortex of the thymic lobule rather than in the medulla. The cortex was mainly represented by lymphocytes and accounted for two-thirds, in the medulla, the medulla consisted mainly of reticuloepithelial cells and corresponded to one-third of the lobule. The location of lymphoblasts is noted mainly in the subcapsular space of the cortex; in some cases, a narrow epithelial space was found under the capsule in rats. In addition, mitotically dividing lymphocytes and a large number of medium and small lymphocytes were more often found in the cortex of the thymic lobules.

The brain substance of the thymus of newborn rat pups was characterized by a reduced number of lymphocytes, between which were located both individual reticular epithelial cells with increased oxyphilia of the cytoplasm, macrophages and monocyte-like cells, and Gassal's thymic bodies.

As a result of our research, against the background of chronic hepatitis of the mother, not only a peculiar dynamics of morphological changes in the thymus of the offspring is revealed, but also, as the results of our research have shown, chronic toxic hepatitis of the mother contributes to the growth retardation in the offspring, expressed in a decrease in body weight by 1-3 days after birth and body lengths of animals, marked 7-14 days after birth. In addition, a decrease in the mass of the thymus of rat pups was established up to 21 days of development (see Table 1, Fig 1, Fig 3).

Table 1.
Influence of toxic maternal hepatitis on some anthropometric parameters and thymus mass in rat pups in the dynamics of early postnatal ontogenesis ($\bar{X} \pm S_x$)

Morphometric indicators of the thymus	A group of animals	Age of animals (in days)					
		1	3	7	15	21	30
Rat weight, g	C	5,6 $\pm$ 0,08	6,0 $\pm$ 0,09	8,9 $\pm$ 0,11	18,6 $\pm$ 0,43	29,1 $\pm$ 0,82	42,3 $\pm$ 0,75
	E	5,1$\pm$0,11	5,3$\pm$0,13	8,1$\pm$0,12	16,9 $\pm$ 0,42	26,8 $\pm$ 0,55	34,7 $\pm$ 1,14
Rat body length, mm	C	27,1 $\pm$ 0,47	33,0 $\pm$ 0,58	44,2 $\pm$ 0,39	51,6 $\pm$ 0,52	55,2 $\pm$ 0,88	57,6 $\pm$ 0,96
	E	23,9 $\pm$ 0,43	27,1 $\pm$ 0,52	36,4$\pm$0,48	41,5$\pm$0,52	47,6$\pm$0,82	51,6 $\pm$ 1,05
Absolute weight of the thymus, g	C	10,1 $\pm$ 0,20	18,1 $\pm$ 0,38	26,4 $\pm$ 0,72	78,5 $\pm$ 3,42	133,0 $\pm$ 6,62	221,0 $\pm$ 4,57
	E	8,3$\pm$0,36	16,0$\pm$0,45	22,9$\pm$0,69	71,9$\pm$3,12	119,6$\pm$4,13	181,6 $\pm$ 4,25
Relative weight of the thymus ($\times 10^{-2}$)	C	0,18 $\pm$ 0,012	0,26 $\pm$ 0,008	0,19 $\pm$ 0,005	0,48 $\pm$ 0,023	0,60 $\pm$ 0,013	0,52 $\pm$ 0,014
	E	0,17$\pm$0,006	0,32$\pm$0,012	0,26$\pm$0,009	0,37$\pm$0,019	0,47$\pm$0,014	0,53 $\pm$ 0,017

Note: 1. conditional abbreviations - group of animals, K - control, O - experienced;

2. the values where the differences are significant are highlighted in bold relative to the previous period at $P < 0.05$.

Table 2.

Influence of toxic maternal hepatitis on the development of structural and functional zones of the thymus of rat pups in the dynamics of early postnatal ontogenesis ($X \pm Sx$)

Day of postnatal development	A group of animals	Thymus zones				Connective tissue stroma	
		Cork		Brain		rel. units	%
		rel. units	%	rel. units	%		
1 day	C	476,8±23,2	74,5	151,6±9,6	23,6	11,6±0,12	1,9
	E	496,6±18,9	77,5	129,3±8,4	20,3	14,1±0,15	2,2
3 days	C	475,5±21,1	74,3	151,7±10,3	23,7	12,8±0,21	2,0
	E	488,8±19,7	76,4	136,5±8,1	21,3	14,7±0,31	2,3
7 days	C	446,7±21,6	69,8	180,5±9,2	24,9	12,8±0,21	2,0
	E	483,2±22,8	75,5	141,4±10,2	22,1	15,4±0,34	2,4
15 days	C	457,6±20,6	71,5	168,3±11,7	26,3	14,1±0,32	2,2
	E	469,8±32,7	73,4	155,5±13,6	24,3	14,7±0,38	2,3
21 days	C	451,8±41,6	70,6	171,6±15,8	26,8	16,6±0,34	2,6
	E	453,2±30,8	69,1	168,6±13,5	27,9	17,2±0,41	3,0
30 days	C	455,0±38,5	71,1	165,8±16,3	25,9	19,2±0,65	3,0
	E	460,2±35,6	71,9	159,3±15,3	24,6	20,5±0,82	3,2

The thymus of newborn rats, an experimental group of animals that developed against the background of toxic maternal hepatitis, is characterized by pronounced structural changes in the processes of differentiation of the thymus into cortical and medulla, in favor of the cortical, which is quite clearly expressed in newborn rat pups. At the same time, it should be noted that the density of distribution of cells in the cortex is markedly reduced. There is a significant decrease in the number of lymphoblasts (by 15%), small lymphocytes (by 20%). The continuation of this trend was characteristic for the subsequent periods of postnatal thymus development. Attention is drawn to the increase in the

number of destructive thymocytes, which at various times after birth exceeded the parameters of the control group by 2-3 times. Along with this, large macrophages with dense inclusions in the cytoplasm, apparently also a sign of increased thymocytolysis, were encountered on the thymus sections of the experimental group much more often than in the control group. The severity of the described changes decreased only by the 30th day of postnatal ontogenesis. Conducted morphometric researches made it possible to establish, only an increase in the area occupied by connective tissue for 1-7 days after delivery (see Table 2, Fig. 2, Fig. 4)

Figure 1. Thymus of a rat in the control group on the 15th day after birth. All structural and functional zones in the thymus lobule are well expressed. Paraffin cut. Hematoxylin-eosin staining. Increased x 130.

Figure 2. Thymus of a rat from the mother with CTG on the 15th day after birth. Visually, an increase in the proportion of the cortical zone relative to the thymus of the control group of animals can be noted. Paraffin cut. Hematoxylin-eosin staining. Increased x 130.

Discussion

Analyzing the results obtained, it is necessary to point out that humans, like many species of mammals, bring immature offspring. To compensate for this immunological immaturity inherent in the period of the fetus and newborn, as well as the first months of life, nature has developed mechanisms of adaptive protection provided by the mother, represented by trans placental transmission of antibodies, anti-infectious resistance factors in the amniotic fluid, and after birth, in colostrum and milk. Therefore, for the full development of the baby, starting from the first day after childbirth, protein components are needed: “the main plastic material”, and, of course, the easily digestible carbohydrates of the mother's milk. In addition, a certain dynamic of the level of hormones in milk is revealed, associated with their participation in the process of metabolic adaptation of newborns to extra uterine existence and causing the restructuring of protein, carbohydrate and fat metabolism in the postnatal period. Colostrum and milk enzymes that enter the body of a newborn during breastfeeding also have a beneficial effect on the processes of its adaptation, affecting the metabolism of proteins and carbohydrates in the intestine [2, 4, 9, 23, 24]. It was found that in the offspring of rats with chronic hepatitis, there is a steady decrease in body weight gain, and a lag in the structural and functional development of the small intestine [14, 15, 16]. Perhaps one of the reasons for these changes during the period of lactotrophic nutrition is the previously discovered decrease in the amount of protein, carbohydrates and enzymatic activity of milk. A decrease in cellular components, apparently, is one of the factors characterizing a decrease in the immunomodulatory function of milk. In addition, a decrease in the number of macrophages, monocytes and lymphocytes, which, on the one hand, contribute to the violation of the transfer of adoptive

immunity. In addition, as indicated in our previous researches, the intake of lysosomes, lipid droplets present in these cells, is significantly reduced. As a result, the trophic influence and immunobiological properties of breast milk are significantly reduced, allowing the child to adapt and survive in the “world of microbes”, where he enters immediately after childbirth [20, 22].

Along with the above, with hepatitis, profound changes in metabolic processes occur, including a violation of protein metabolism, which, naturally, affects the hormonal balance, and, consequently, the development of the placenta and mammary gland, as well as the developing offspring. It is also necessary to take into account the immunodeficiency condition of the mother with hepatitis, it becomes clear what is the reason for the lag in the development of the digestive and immune systems of the offspring, established by many researchers [8, 11]. In addition, it has been shown that the process of chronic heliotronic hepatitis is accompanied by profound morphological changes in the body's immune system. These changes lead to an imbalance between the T and B systems of the immune system and the development of an autoimmune process [2, 3, 13, 22]. Summarizing all the above causal relationships, we can assume that they could contribute to the morphological changes in the thymus of the offspring of mothers with chronic toxic hepatitis during breastfeeding.

CONCLUSIONS

Thereby, with chronic toxic hepatitis (CTG) of the mother, the development of the offspring has a negative effect, expressed in a decrease in the weight of rat pups by 1-3 days and a growth retardation is most pronounced at 7-14 after birth, there is also a decrease in the weight of the thymus up to 21 days of development. Morphologically, in the thymus of offspring born from female rats with chronic heliotronic hepatitis, in the dynamics of the period of breastfeeding, hypoplasia and a lag in the development of structural and functional

zones of the organ are noted, due to an increase in the area occupied by the connective tissue stroma. Therefore, prophylactic treatment of pups from mothers with toxic hepatitis is necessary, most likely, starting from the antenatal period and continuing during breastfeeding.

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